

Fluxes in Classical and Quantum Mechanics

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The spatial density of a bound system in classical mechanics can be described by $1/v(x)$ where $v(x)$ is the velocity obtained from a conservation of energy equation. This density can increase and decrease even though there is one particle and so it would be good to understand why. In addition, quantum mechanical density approaches $1/v(x)$ in places for high energy eigenvalues and so the same classical ideas may apply to the quantum case. We try to examine both of these cases. In addition, we consider describing quantum mechanics in terms of fluxes. At first glance, these appear classical in form, but really are not as they apply for all energy eigenvalues and not just in high energy eigenvalue limits. We consider momentum and energy fluxes which look almost like statistical mechanical quantities with the added factor of $\cos(px)$ which we argue comes from a forward-backward bouncing nature of quantum particles. As a result, it seems that even for high energy eigenvalues, quantum mechanics is different from classical mechanics, and that the latter may be coarse graining of the former.

Classical Spatial Density

The classical spatial density of a bound classical particle (say on a spring) can be given by $dt = dx/v(x)$ where $v(x)$ is obtained from a conservation of energy equation (1). This density can increase or decrease, yet there is only one particle in question. To attempt to see what is happening, consider a one dimensional length being cut into equal tiny units dx and time being cut into equal tiny units of dt . Next, consider the time it takes for the particle to move through a unit dx i.e.:

$dx = v(x) dt_1$ Here dt_1 indicates this time is not the same as the equal time unit dt

Next, one may ask how many particles on average were in dx during dt . This should be related to the density.

Density $dx = (0 (dt - dt_1) + 1 dt_1) / dt = dt_1/dt = dx/v(x) (1/dt)$ with $(1/dt)$ being a constant.

Thus, if a particle spends less time in one dx region than in another, the density drops as one considers equal dt time units for making a density measurement. Given that quantum mechanics is supposed to approach the $1/v(x)$ density in places, this scenario may have relevance for the quantum case.

Quantum Mechanics

In quantum mechanics, one starts with plane waves $\exp(-ikx)$ and $\exp(ikx)$ moving forward and backwards. One may ask for the meaning of these math functions. It should be noted that the first represents a moving radius of unit 1 and angle kx in a clockwise direction and the other in a counterclockwise direction. For each dx , the angle is kdx so it appears that the motion of the radius corresponds to constant motion on the x axis. Thus, derivatives of the function $\exp(ikx)$ give dynamical information. Now $\exp(ikx) = \cos(kx) + i \sin(kx)$ and $\exp(-ikx) = \cos(kx) - i \sin(kx)$ so adding the two yields $2\cos(kx)$. One may ask what is the meaning of this period function along the x -axis.

In a 2×2 matrix model (2), one can linearize in energy Einstein's 1905 energy-momentum equation by using 2×2 matrices. It is assumed that the vectors $(1,0)$ and $(0,1)$ represent backward and forward motion, so the energy eigenvector is a combination of these two. In other words, a particle that moves on average with velocity v in one direction, is actually moving back and forth as it moves along. If there are differing speeds during this forward and backward motion, it seems there should be different "spatial densities", just as in the classical case of $1/v(x)$. Thus, it seems that momentum at a point is not proportional to p , but to $p \cos(kx)$. (One could use $\sin(kx)$ depending on boundary conditions.) This seems to imply, just as in the classical case, that one is breaking space-time into equal $dx dt$ units. A particle with momentum p undergoes a cycle with different internal speeds which affect the probability because it spends less time in one $dx dt$ unit than in another. The $\cos(px)$ term seems to describe motion in a center of mass frame as it is this "extra" motion which is causing the density changes in space for a plane wave. This leads to interesting averages being calculated for many waves (stirred up by a potential), namely:

$$\text{Average kinetic energy} = [\text{Sum on } p \quad p^2/2m \text{ } f_p \cos(px)] / [\text{Sum on } p \text{ } f_p \cos(px)]$$

Here f_p is a weight factor for p , \hbar is set to 1 and the denominator is a normalization factor. It was argued in (3), that $\text{Sum on } p \text{ } p \cos(px)$ called the wavefunction, when squared, gives physical density. It should be noted that because $\cos(kx)$ contains symmetry, it is as if it is measuring the density fluctuations in a center of mass frame, but derivatives are giving the average momentum in lab frame.

These averages can in fact, include negative contributions from $\cos(px)$. In such a case, it seems that negative values are associated with backward motion in the center of mass frame and are important because one is dealing with flow (it seems). For the classical case, the spatial density is always positive $1/v(x)$ even though $v(x)$ can be positive or negative.

If one considers a single plane wave, then one has $p^2/2m \cos(px)/\cos(px)$, so one obtains the classical value at each point. Thus, it seems that it is only when one has a collection of plane waves that differing values of $\cos(k_j x)$ for differing k_j values is important. For a given dx and dt different k_j values represent different densities in dx measured over dt and the relative flow direction of the internal motion cycle of a particle is important as backward motion is sending kinetic energy in the backward direction.

These forward and backward flows also affect the physical density which is equal to the wavefunction squared. It should be remembered that it seems that density is measured at each dx during dt and so fast moving particles contribute less and backward moving particles can decrease momentum in places.

Flow in Quantum Mechanics

Given the above descriptions, it seems that quantum mechanics can be described in terms of flow. Let us first consider a wavefunction $W(x) = \sum_p f_p \cos(px)$ and a density = $W(x)W(x)$. Then:

$$d/dx \text{ density}(x) = 2W(x) d/dx(W(x)). \quad ((1))$$

It was noted that for the case of a forward and backward plane wave, one has $2\cos(kx)$ and the derivative yields information about the momentum. Thus it seems that one can think of ((1)) as being a kind of flux equation with $2W(x) d/dx W(x) = \text{density}(x) u(x)$ where $u(x)$ is a velocity defined by $d/dx W(x) / W(x)$. microscopically this is in keeping with the equation:

$[\sum_p -p \sin(px) f_p] / W(x)$ with $W(x)$ being a normalization constant. Thus, in quantum mechanics, it seems that the density changes due to 2×2 matrix particle plane wave momentum flow.

Next, consider conservation of energy in quantum mechanics (i.e. the time independent Schrodinger equation):

$$[\sum_p p^2/2m f_p \cos(px)] / W(x) + V(x) = E_n \quad \text{where } E_n \text{ is a particular energy eigenvalue.}$$

The change in the first term, equal to $-dV(x)/dx$ the classical force, can be written as $d/dx (-1/2m) [(d/dx)(d/dx) W(x)] / W(x)$ or:

$$(d/dx)^3 W(x) / W(x) - [(d/dx)^2 W(x) d/dx W(x)] / W(x)^2$$

((2))

Both of these terms are interesting. The first appears to be a flux of carrying away kinetic energy. In classical mechanics, one might write $p^2/2m * p$. In quantum mechanics, one has the added effect that the internal 2×2 matrix motion, namely $\cos(px)$ (or $\sin(px)$ depending on boundary conditions). The second term is a product of the average classical kinetic energy $.5m v(x)*v(x) = -d/dx)^2 W(x) / W(x)$ and $d/dx W(x) / W(x)$ or $u(x)$ related to the change in density. Thus, the classical force has the effect of causing ((2)) in quantum mechanics.

Next, consider energy densities. The conservation of energy equation multiplied by density can be written as:

$$W(x)W(x) \cdot \frac{1}{2} m v(x)^2 + V(x) W(x)W(x) = E W(x)W(x) \quad ((3))$$

This is a completely classical looking equation, but density $W(x)W(x)$ and average kinetic energy $\frac{1}{2} m v(x)^2$ are calculated quantum mechanically. Consider evaluating ((3)) at $x+dx$. This leads to:

$$W(x)W(x) \left[\frac{\sum \cos(px)}{\sum \cos(px)} \right] / W(x) + \left[\frac{d}{dx} V(x) \right] W(x)W(x) = (E - V(x)) \frac{d}{dx} [W(x)W(x)]$$

Now $(E - V(x)) = \frac{1}{2} m v(x)^2$ and $\frac{d}{dx} [W(x)W(x)]$ can be written as $[W(x)W(x)]u(x)$

Then the effect of microscopic kinetic energy flux equals classical force plus an average kinetic energy flux:

$$\left[\frac{\sum \cos(px)}{\sum \cos(px)} \right] / W(x) = -\text{Classical force} + \frac{1}{2} m v(x)^2 u(x) \quad ((4))$$

Thus, one can describe quantum mechanics for any energy eigenvalue in terms of somewhat classical looking flux-flow equations.

Comparison with Classical Physics

Many papers (4),(5) compare average quantum mechanical type quantities to classical mechanical equations or use wavepackets. In this note, we try to argue that classical type flow equations already exist in quantum mechanics. Furthermore, we suggest that a particle like an electron is really a 2x2 matrix type particle which bounces back and forth and that this governs the "wave type" motion of quantum mechanics. This wave motion does not disappear even for high energy eigenvalues. It is only an envelope over the density which approaches $1/v(x)$. For the oscillator one can see that there are still quantum mechanical humps which approach $1/v(x)$ near peak values. Thus, it seems that classical mechanics may be a kind of coarse graining of quantum mechanics. If one only sees the humps, which represent densities close to $1/v(x)$, one might think that one has a continuous density of $1/v(x)$ which washes over quantum effects which still exist.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have tried to explain increases and decreases in spatial density when classical mechanics is described by a density of $1/v(x)$. It seems space time is broken into equally spaced dx and dt portions and that density varies because the time spent by a particle in dx can be less than dt . We try to carry over these ideas to quantum mechanics with the added idea that quantum particles have a fundamental backward forward motion which also affects the density. Next, we argue that quantum mechanics for any energy eigenvalue can be written in

terms of classical looking flow equations. Finally, we argue that classical mechanics is a kind of coarse graining of quantum mechanics.

References

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